

COMPARATIVE ECONOMICS OF DRILL PADDY BASED CROPPING SYSTEMS IN GADCHIROLI DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study has been undertaken in Gadchiroli district of Vidarbha. Gadchiroli is one of the major paddy growing district of Vidarbha and it falls under the high rainfall zone. Paddy is the major kharif crop grown in the district. The cropping pattern of the district is dominated by the paddy crop Two tahsils of the Gadchiroli district namely Chamorshi, and Armori were selected for the study. Now a days farmers in these tahsils are practising drill paddy cultivation with the help of Krishi Vidyan Kendra, Gadchiroli and Maharashtra State Agriculture Department. From each tahsil three villages were selected and from each village fifteen farmers were selected randomly. In all 90 farmers were selected for the present study. For each drill paddy based cropping system 30 farmers were selected. Among the different types of drill paddy-based cropping system cultivation group higher percentage of illiteracy was observed in the farmers adopted drill paddy- latharus cropping system (26.66%) followed by drill paddy-linseed group (19.99%) and drill paddy-gram (6.66%). Percentage of farmers having graduate level education was highest in the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system (13.33%) followed by drill paddy-linseed and drill paddy- latharus cropping systems (6.66%). The average size of holding of the group of farmers adopted the drill paddy-gram cropping system was 2.52 hectare followed by drill paddy-linseed 2.08 hectare and drill paddy- latharus 1.82 hectare. The highest cropping intensity was observed in the farmers group adopted drill paddy- gram cropping system (197.37%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (195.79%), and drill paddy- latharus cropping system (190.32%) respectively. Paddy occupied 52.54 % area of GCA in the group of farmers adopted drill paddy-latharus cropping system followed by farmers group of drill paddy-linseed (51.07%), and drill paddy-gram (50.66%) respectively. The average investments in fixed assets by the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system was Rs 10,73000/farm followed by drill paddy-linseed cropping system Rs.9,01500/farm, and for drill paddy-latharus Rs. 7,96000/farm respectively. The highest gross returns received to farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system i.e. Rs.1,40000/- per hectare followed by drill paddy-linseed Rs 97,570/-, and drill paddy-latharus cropping system Rs.87,600/-. Highest per hectare net returns at cost A realised by the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system Rs.88,505.05/- followed by paddy- linseed Rs.57,100.89/- and paddy-latharus Rs.46,263.35/- The highest BC ratio was realised by the farmers adopted drill paddy- gram cropping system at Cost A, Cost B and Cost C respectively followed by drill paddy-linseed and drill paddy-latharus cropping system.

Keywords - major paddy, cropping system, average investments, cropping system.

Introduction and Objectives:

India is the second largest rice growing country after China. Besides, this nation has a large range of area under rice cultivation, as it is one of the important nutrient staple crop. Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a staple food for about 65% of the population in India. It plays a vital role in strengthening food and livelihood security. Despite having stagnant area during the last decade, the rice production has registered an increase of 18% but there is a common concern about declining profitability in paddy production. India produces 107 million tonnes of rice in an area of 44 million ha. which constitutes about 35% of area and 40% of production of the food grain in the country. It is a staple food of about 65% of the country's population, which itself indicates its importance in the food security of the country. Paddy production generates employment of about 3.5 billion-man days and contributes about 10% of Agricultural GDP in the country. Paddy is considered 'water guzzler' and the unfavourable monsoon adversely affects its area, production and productivity in the country.

Paddy is predominant cereal crop of Maharashtra grown under diverse conditions in the state from almost sea level of Kokan to an elevation of 2000 feet in malva tract and extreme Eastern Vidarbha Zone in Bhandara, Gondia, Gadchiroli and Chandrapur districts. It is cultivated under wide range of soils and climatic condition. It is grown in coastal as well as heavy clay loam soils. In many parts of the state as well as in the Gadchiroli district, paddy is grown as a sole crop for consumption and as a cash crop. The cultivation of high yielding varieties of paddy is increasing in the Gadchiroli district but the yield as compared to other

state is low. The cropping pattern of Gadchiroli district is dominated by paddy crop and the share in gross cropped area is about 70%. Therefore, it is felt necessary to study the cost of cultivation of drill paddy-based cropping systems in Gadchiroli District.

Project Objectives

The present study has undertaken with following specific objectives:

To identify the existing drill Paddy based cropping systems.

To study the socio-economic characteristics of selected farmers of drill Paddy based cropping systems.

To analyse the economics of different drill Paddy based cropping systems.

Methodology:

The present study has been undertaken in Gadchiroli district of Vidarbha. Gadchiroli is one of the major paddy growing district of Vidarbha and it falls under the high rainfall zone. Paddy is the major kharif crop grown in the district. The cropping pattern of the district is dominated by the paddy crop.

Selection of sample

Two tahsils of the Gadchiroli district namely Chamorshi, and Armori were selected for the study. Now a days farmers in these tahsils are practising drill paddy cultivation with the help of Krishi Vidyan Kendra, Gadchiroli and Maharashtra State Agriculture Department. From each tahsil three villages were selected and from each village fifteen farmers were selected randomly. In all 90 farmers were selected for the present study. For each drill paddy based cropping system 30 farmers were selected. The details of selected sample are given below.

Table 1. The details of selected sample

Sr.No.	Name of tahsil	Name of Village	No. farmers
1	Chamorshi	Bhendada	15
		Dhotkuli	15
		Jairampur	15

2	Armori	Shirni	15
		Koregaon	15
		Akapur	15
Total no. of farmers selected for the study			90

Collection of data

The data on various aspects of the study were collected from the selected cultivators by personal interviews with the help of specially designed scheduled. The data pertains to the crop year 2022-23.

Analysis of data

Identification of drill paddy-based cropping systems

Drill paddy-based cropping systems were identified by conducting special survey and discussion with the farmers. The selected drill paddy based cropping systems were (1) Drill paddy-gram (2) Drill paddy-linseed and (3) Drill paddy-latharus.

Socio- economic characteristics

Second objective of study was achieved by simple tabular analysis.

Following characteristics of the selected farmers were studied.

Family size and its composition

Educational status

Land use pattern

Cropping pattern

Investment in fixed capital assets

Family size and its composition

Table 1. Average family size and its composition of drill paddy farmers

(Figure in no.)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Drill Paddy Cropping Systems		
		Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - Latharus
1	Male	3.60 (36.00)	2.80 (33.45)	2.62 (33.85)
2	Female	3.44 (34.40)	2.72 (32.49)	2.46 (31.78)
3	Children	2.96 (29.60)	2.85 (34.06)	2.66 (34.36)
	Total	10.00 (100.00)	8.37 (100.00)	7.74 (100.00)

Note: Figures in the parentheses indicate the percentages to the respective total.

The information about the average family size and its composition is presented in table 1. It can be seen from the table that the average family size of the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system was 10.00 members followed by drill paddy - linseed 8.37, and drill paddy - latharus 7.74 respectively. Among the group the highest proportion of male was seen in adopting drill paddy - gram cropping system (36.00%) followed by drill paddy - latharus (33.85%), and drill paddy - linseed (33.45%). The highest proportion of female was in

Economics of drill paddy-based cropping systems

For working out the economics of drill paddy cultivation followed by other crops the cost of cultivation was worked out by using standard cost concepts i.e. cost A, cost B and cost C.

Results and Discussion:

Identification of drill paddy-based cropping systems

The present study deals with the comparative economics of drill paddy-based cropping systems. Drill paddy-based cropping systems were identified by conducting special survey and discussion with the farmers and are identified as follows under rainfed condition:

Drill Paddy - Gram

Drill Paddy - Linseed

Drill Paddy - Latharus

(2) Socioeconomic characteristics of the selected farmers

The socio-economic parameters of the farmers influenced the production, income and marketing activities of the farm business. These factors are explained below.

adopting drill paddy - gram cropping system (34.40%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (32.49%), and drill paddy - latharus (31.78%).

In case of children highest proportion was seen in the farmers group adopting drill paddy - latharus cropping system (34.36%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (34.06%) and drill paddy - gram (29.60%).

Educational status

Education of the family is another factor influencing the skill, ability to use scarce resources and adoption of new technology. The information regarding educational status of the family is presented in table 2.

Table 2. Educational status of the selected farmers

SN	Particulars	Drill Paddy Cropping Systems		
		Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - latharus
1	Illiterate	2 (6.66)	6 (19.99)	8 (26.66)
2	Primary (1 st to 7 th standard)	4 (13.33)	10 (33.33)	14 (46.66)
3	Secondary (8 th to 10 th standard)	12 (39.99)	8 (26.66)	4 (13.33)
4	Higher secondary (11 th to 12 th standard)	8 (26.66)	4 (13.33)	2 (6.66)
5	Graduates (college education)	4 (13.33)	2 (6.66)	2 (6.66)
	Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)

It was observed from the table 2 that among the different types of dill paddy cropping system cultivation group higher percentage of illiteracy was observed in the farmers adopting drill paddy - latharus cropping system (26.66%) followed by dill paddy - linseed group (19.99%), and drill paddy - gram (6.66%). Thus, least illiteracy was found among the farmers adopting drill paddy - gram cropping system. Percentage of higher secondary education was higher in the farmers adopting drill paddy - gram cropping system (26.66%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (13.33%) and least percentage of higher secondary education was observed in the farmers adopting drill paddy - latharus cropping system i.e. (6.66%).

Table 3. Average land use pattern of selected farmers.

Percentage of farmers having graduate level education was highest in the farmers adopted drill paddy - gram cropping system (13.33%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (6.66%) and drill paddy - latharus (6.66%).

Land use pattern

Land utilization indicates the area of land actually utilized for different purposes like crop production, fallow and net cultivated land etc. The result presented in table 3 indicates the land use pattern of selected farmers.

(Area in hectare)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Drill Paddy Cropping Systems		
		Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - Latharus
1	Total land holding	2.52 (100.00)	2.08 (100.00)	1.82 (100.00)
2	Current fallow land	0.23 (9.13)	0.18 (8.65)	0.27 (14.84)
3	Net cultivated area	2.29 (90.87)	1.90 (91.35)	1.55 (85.16)
4	Gross cropped area	4.52 (179.36)	3.72 (178.85)	2.95 (162.08)
5	Cropping intensity	197.37	195.79	190.32

The average size of holding of the group of farmers adopted the drill paddy - gram, drill paddy - linseed and drill paddy - latharus cropping systems was 2.52, 2.08, and 1.82 hectares respectively. It could be observed that the proportion of net cropped area to total holding was highest in the group of farmers adopted drill paddy - linseed cropping

(D) Cropping pattern

Table.4 Cropping pattern of selected farmers

system (91.35%) followed by drill paddy - gram (90.87%), and drill paddy - latharus (85.16%) respectively. The highest cropping intensity was observed in the farmers group adopted the cropping systems i.e drill paddy – gram (197.37%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (195.79%) and drill paddy - latharus (190.32%) respectively.

(Area in hect.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - latharus
1	Paddy	2.29 (50.66)	1.90 (51.07)	1.55 (52.54)
2	Gram	2.13 (47.13)	1.80 (48.38)	-
3	Linseed	-	1.80 (48.38)	-
4	Latharus	-	-	1.40 (47.46)
5	Others	0.10 (2.22)	0.02 (0.54)	-
	Gross cropped area	4.52 (100.00)	3.72 (100.00)	2.95 (100.00)

It is also an important factor influencing the returns from the farm business. The cropping pattern followed by the selected cultivators is presented in table 4. Data presented in table 4 reveals that paddy occupied 52.54 % area of GCA in the group of farmers adopted drill paddy - latharus cropping system followed by farmers group of drill paddy - linseed and drill paddy - gram i.e (around 50.00%).After the

Table 5. Per farm investment in different capital asset

paddy proportion of linseed was more which accounted 48.38 % in case of farmers adopted dill paddy - linseed cropping system.

Investment in fixed capital assets

The information on per farm investment in different capital asset such as land, farm buildings, implements, machinery and livestock are given in table 5.

(Rs. /farm)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - Latharus
1	Land	966000 (90.03)	820000 (90.95)	735000 (92.34)
2	Buildings	18000.00 (1.67)	12000.00 (1.33)	9000.00 (1.13)

3	Cattle shed	13000.00 (0.21)	9500.00 (1.05)	8500.00 (1.07)
4	Implement & machinery	16000.00 (1.49)	12000.00 (1.33)	7500.00 (0.94)
5	Livestock	60000.00 (5.59)	48000.00 (5.33)	36000.00 (4.52)
	Total	10,73000 (100.00)	9,01500 (100.00)	7,96000 (100.00)

From the table 5 it is observed that the average investments in fixed assets by the farmers adopted drill paddy - gram cropping system was Rs 10,73000 / farm followed by drill paddy - linseed cropping system Rs. 9,01500 /farm, and for drill paddy - latharus farmers Rs. 7,96000/farm respectively. The investment in land alone were around 92.34 % to 90.03% of the selected farmers who are adopted different drill paddy cropping systems. Next to land the investment in livestock were around 5.59% to 4.52 %.

(A) Drill paddy - Gram cropping system –The economics of cost of cultivation of drill paddy - gram cropping system is presented in table 6 & 7.

(1) Drill paddy -It could be seen from the table 6 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs.31472.91/- per hectare in the cultivation of paddy by drilling method. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 48698.57/- and Rs. 51168.57/- respectively. Among the direct expenses the share of human labour in total cost was highest (15.66%) followed by machine charges (12.51%). The share of cost A in total cost was (61.51%). In cost B the highest share in total cost was of rental value of land (23.512%) followed by interest on fixed capital (10.16 %). The cost B is accounted for (95.17%) of the total cost. The share of family labour in total cost was 4.82%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 1741.73/-.

Table 6. Per hectare cost of cultivation of paddy by drilling method (Drill Paddy- Gram)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	8.00	280.00	2240.00	4.37
		Female	Days	34.00	170.00	5780.00	11.29
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	3.00	700.00	2100.00	4.11
3	Machine charges		Hours	8.00	800.00	6400.00	12.51
4	Seed		Kgs	50.00	40.00	2000.00	3.91
5	Manures		Qtls	22.00	85.00	1870.00	3.65
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	72.00	12.40	892.80	1.74
		P	Kgs	40.00	47.00	1880.00	3.67
		K	Kgs	18.00	35.50	639.00	1.25
	Total					3411.8	6.67
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			2500.00	4.88
8	Herbicides					1950.00	3.81
9	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			120.00	0.24
10	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			130.00	0.25
11	Working capital	Cost	Rs			28501.80	55.71
12	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			1710.11	3.34
13	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			1220.00	2.38
14	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			41.00	0.08
15	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			31472.91	61.51
16	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			12025.66	23.51
17	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			5200.00	10.16
18	Cost B					48698.57	95.17
19	Family human labour	Male	Days	7.00	280.00	1960.00	3.83
		Female	Days	3.00	170.00	510.00	0.99
20	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			51168.57	100.00
21	Yield per hectare		Qtls	28.00	2500.00	70000.00	
22	Value of by-produce		Qtls	24.00	100.00	2400.00	
23	Per quintal cost of main produce					1741.73	

Table 7. Per hectare cost of cultivation of Gram (Drill Paddy- Gram)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	4.00	280.00	1120.00	2.98
		Female	Days	6.00	170.00	1020.00	2.72
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	2.00	700.00	1400.00	3.73
3	Machine charges		Hours	6.00	400.00	2400.00	6.39
4	Seed		Kgs	80.00	120.00	9600.00	25.59

5	Manures		Qtls	6.00	85.00	510.00	1.36
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	2.08
		P	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	2.08
		K	Kgs	5.0	86.95	434.75	1.16
		Total				1999.85	5.33
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			950.00	2.53
8	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			80.00	0.22
9	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			90.00	0.24
10	Working capital	Cost	Rs			19169.85	51.12
11	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			1150.19	3.07
12	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			480.00	1.28
13	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			22.00	0.06
14	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			20822.04	55.53
15	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			11378.00	30.34
16	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			3500.00	9.33
17	Cost B					35700.04	95.20
18	Family human labour	Male	Days	4.00	280.00	1120.00	2.98
		Female	Days	4.00	170.00	680.00	1.82
19	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			37500.04	100.00
20	Yield per hectare		Qtls	11.00	6000.00	66000	
21	Value of by-produce		Qtls	12.00	200.00	2400.00	
22	Per quintal cost of main produce					3190.91	

Gram - The economics of cost of cultivation of gram is presented in table 7. It is observed from the table 7 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs. 20822.04/- per hectare in the cultivation of gram. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 35700.04/- and Rs. 37500.04/- respectively. Among the direct expenses the share of seed expenses in total cost was highest (25.59%) followed by machine charges (6.39 %). The share of cost A in total cost was (55.53). In cost B the highest share in total cost was of rental value of land (30.34%) followed by interest on fixed capital (9.33%). The cost B is accounted for (95.20%) of the total cost. The share of family labour in total cost was 4.8%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 3190.91/-.

Drill paddy - Linseed cropping system -The economics of cost of cultivation of drill paddy - linseed cropping system is presented in table 8 & 9.

Drill paddy -It could be seen from the table 8 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs.30378.15/- per hectare in the cultivation of paddy by drilling method. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 46714.15/- and Rs. 50084.15/- respectively. Among the direct expenses

the share of human labour in total cost was highest (14.78%) followed by machine charges (12.78%). The share of cost A in total cost was (60.65%). In cost B the highest share in total cost was of rental value of land (22.83%) followed by interest on fixed capital (9.78 %). The cost B is accounted for (93.27%) of the total cost. The share of family labour in total cost was 6.72%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 1797.15/-.

Linseed - The economics of cost of cultivation of linseed is presented in table 9. It is observed from the table 9 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs. 10090.96/- per hectare in the cultivation of linseed. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 19440.62/- and Rs. 22420.62/- respectively. Among the direct expenses the share of human labour was 17.61% followed by fertilizer expenses (8.92 %). The share of cost A in total cost was (45.00%). In cost B the highest share in total cost was of rental value of land (21.18%) followed by interest on fixed capital (20.52%). The cost B is accounted for (86.71%) of the total cost. The share of family labour in total cost was 13.29%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 5068.32/-.

Table 8. Per hectare cost of cultivation of paddy by drilling method

(Drill Paddy- Linseed)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	7.00	280.00	1960.00	3.92
		Female	Days	32.00	170.00	5440.00	10.86
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	3.00	700.00	2100.00	4.19
3	Machine charges		Hours	8.00	800.00	6400.00	12.78
4	Seed		Kgs	52.00	40.00	2080.00	4.15
5	Manures		Qtls	18.00	85.00	1530.00	3.05
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	72.00	12.40	892.80	1.78
		P	Kgs	40.00	47.00	1880.00	3.75
		K	Kgs	18.00	35.50	639.00	1.27
		Total				3411.80	6.82
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			2372.00	4.74
8	Herbicides					2000.00	3.99
9	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			140.00	0.28
10	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			122.00	0.24

11	Working capital	Cost	Rs			27555.80	55.02
12	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			1653.35	3.26
13	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			1130.00	2.26
14	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			39.00	0.07
15	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			30378.15	60.65
16	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			11436.00	22.83
17	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			4900.00	9.78
18	Cost B					46714.15	93.27
19	Family human labour	Male	Days	9.00	280.00	2520.00	5.03
		Female	Days	5.00	170.00	850.00	1.69
20	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			50084.15	100.00
21	Yield per hectare		Qtls	26.70	2500.00	66750.00	
22	Value of by-produce		Qtls	21.00	100.00	2100.00	
23	Per quintal cost of main produce					1797.15	

Table 9. Per hectare cost of cultivation of Linseed (Drill Paddy- Linseed)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	7.00	280.00	1960.00	8.74
		Female	Days	7.00	170.00	1190.00	8.87
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	2.00	700.00	1400.00	6.24
3	Machine charges		Hours	-	-	-	-
4	Seed		Kgs	20.00	70.00	1400.00	6.24
5	Manures		Qtls	6.00	85.00	510.00	2.27
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	3.49
		P	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	3.49
		K	Kgs	5.00	86.95	434.75	1.94
	Total					1999.85	8.92
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			-	
8	Herbicides					-	
9	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			120.00	0.54
10	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			122.00	0.55
11	Working capital	Cost	Rs			8701.85	38.81
12	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			522.11	2.33
13	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			830.00	3.71
14	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			37.00	0.16
15	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			10090.96	45.00
16	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			4749.66	21.18
17	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			4600.00	20.52
18	Cost B					19440.62	86.71
19	Family human labour	Male	Days	7.00	280.00	1960.00	8.74
		Female	Days	6.00	170.00	1020.00	4.55
20	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			22420.62	100.00
21	Yield per hectare		Qtls	4.40	6500.00	28600.00	
22	Value of by-produce		Qtls	4.00	30.00	120.00	
23	Per quintal cost of main produce					5068.32	

Drill paddy - Latharus cropping system –The economics of cost of cultivation of drill paddy - latharus cropping system is presented in table 10 & 11.

Drill paddy –It could be seen from the table 10 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs.30458.41/- per hectare in the cultivation of paddy by drilling method. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 46336.07/- and Rs. 49986.07/- respectively. Among the direct expenses the share of human labour in total cost was highest (17.06%) followed by machine charges (11.21%). The share of cost A in total cost was (60.93%). In cost B the highest share in total cost was of rental value of land (22.36%) followed by interest on fixed capital (9.41 %). The cost B is accounted for (92.69%) of the total cost. The share of family labour

in total cost was 7.31%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 1839.16/-.

Latharus - The economics of cost of cultivation of latharus is presented in table 11. It is observed from the table 11 that farmers incurred an expenditure (Cost A) of Rs. 10878.24/- per hectare in the cultivation of latharus. The per hectare cost B and cost C was Rs. 18132.57/- and Rs. 19712.57/- respectively. Among the direct expenses the share of seed in total cost was highest (19.78%) followed by human labour (16.09 %). The share of cost A in total cost was (55.18%). The cost B is accounted for (91.98%) of the total cost. The share of family labour in total cost was 8.01%. The per quintal cost of main produce is Rs. 4853.14/-.

Table 10. Per hectare cost of cultivation of paddy by drilling method (Drill Paddy- Latharus)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	8.00	280.00	2240.00	4.48
		Female	Days	37.00	170.00	6290.00	12.58
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	3.00	700.00	2100.00	4.21
3	Machine charges		Hours	7.00	800.00	5600.00	11.21
4	Seed		Kgs	48.00	40.00	1920.00	3.84
5	Manures		Qtls	15.00	85.00	1275.00	2.55
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	72.00	12.40	892.80	1.78
		P	Kgs	40.00	47.00	1880.00	3.76
		K	Kgs	18.00	35.50	639.00	1.28
	Total					3411.80	6.83
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			2400.00	4.81
8	Herbicides					1950.00	3.91
9	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			120.00	0.24
10	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			70.00	0.14
11	Working capital	Cost	Rs			27376.80	54.77
12	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			1642.61	3.28
13	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			1400.00	2.80
14	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			39.00	0.08
15	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			30458.41	60.93
16	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			11177.66	22.36
17	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			4700.00	9.41
18	Cost B					46336.07	92.69
19	Family human labour	Male	Days	10.00	280.00	2800.00	5.61
		Female	Days	5.00	170.00	850.00	1.70
20	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			49986.07	100.00
21	Yield per hectare		Qtls	26.20	2500.00	65500.00	
22	Value of by-produce		Qtls	18.00	100.00	1800.00	
23	Per quintal cost of main produce					1839.16	

Table 11. Per hectare cost of cultivation of Latharus (Drill Paddy- Latharus)

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost per unit of input	Total cost per ha. (Rs)	% to total cost
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	4.00	280.00	1120.00	5.68
		Female	Days	12.00	170.00	2040.00	10.35
2	Bullock labour		(Pair days)	1.00	700.00	700.00	3.55
3	Machine charges		Hours	-	-	-	-
4	Seed		Kgs	65.00	60.00	3900.00	19.78
5	Manures		Qtls	-	-	-	-
6	Fertilizer	N	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	3.97
		P	Kgs	9.00	86.95	782.55	3.97
		K	Kgs	5.00	86.95	434.75	2.21
	Total					1999.85	10.15
7	Insecticide	Cost	Rs.			-	-
8	Herbicides					-	-
9	Incidental charges	Cost	Rs.			120.00	0.61
10	Repairing charges	Cost	Rs.			110.00	0.56
11	Working capital	Cost	Rs			9989.85	50.67
12	Interest on working capital	Cost	Rs.			599.39	3.04
13	Depreciation	Cost	Rs.			260.00	1.32
14	Land revenue	Cost	Rs.			29.00	0.15
15	Cost (A)	Cost	Rs.			10878.24	55.18
16	Rental value of land	Cost	Rs.			3354.33	17.02
17	Interest on fixed capital	Cost	Rs.			3900.00	19.78
18	Cost B					18132.57	91.98
19	Family human labour	Male	Days	2.00	280.00	560.00	2.84
		Female	Days	6.00	170.00	1020.00	5.17

20	Cost C	Cost	Rs.			19712.57	100.00
21	Yield per hectare		Qtls	4.00	5000.00	20000.00	
22	Value of by-produce		Qtls	3.00	100.00	300.00	
23	Per quintal cost of main produce					4853.14	

Comparative economics of drill paddy-based cropping systems- The comparative economics of different drill paddy-based cropping systems is presented in table 12. It is observed from the table that the highest BC ratio was realised by the farmers adopting drill paddy - gram cropping system. However, all the drill paddy-based cropping systems are economically feasible.

Table 12. Comparative economics of different drill paddy-based cropping systems

Sr. No.	Particular	Drill Paddy Cropping Systems		
		Drill Paddy-Gram	Drill Paddy - Linseed	Drill Paddy - Latharus
1	Yield per hect.	Paddy-28.00 Gram-11.00	Paddy-26.70 Linseed-4.40	Paddy-26.20 Latharus-4.00
2	Value of main produce	Paddy-70,000 Gram-66,000	Paddy-66,758 Linseed-28,600	Paddy-65,500 Latharus-20,000
3	Value of by-produce	Paddy-2400 Gram-2400	Paddy-2100 Linseed-120	Paddy-1800 Latharus-300
4	Gross returns	Paddy-72,400 Gram-68,400	Paddy-68,850 Linseed-28,720	Paddy-67,300 Latharus-20,300
5	Total Gross returns	1,40,800	97,530	87,600
6	i)Cost A	Paddy-31472.91 Gram-20822.04	Paddy-30,378.15 Linseed-10,090.96	Paddy-30,458.41 Latharus-10,878.24
7	Total of Cost A	52,294.95	40,469.11	41,336.65
	ii)Cost B	Paddy-48,698.57 Gram-35,700.04	Paddy-46,714.15 Linseed-19,440.62	Paddy-46,336.07 Latharus-18,132.57
8	Total of Cost B	84,398.61	66,154.77	64,468.64
	iii)Cost C	Paddy-51,168.57 Gram-37,500.04	Paddy-50,084.15 Linseed-22,420.62	Paddy-49,986.07 Latharus-19,712.57
9	Total of Cost C	88,668.61	72,504.77	69,698.64
10	Net returns at cost A	88,505.05	57,100.89	46,263.35
11	Net returns at cost B	56,401.39	31,415.23	23131.36
12	Net returns at cost C	52,131.39	25,065.23	17,901.36
13	BC ratio at cost A	2.69	2.41	2.11
13	BC ratio at cost C	1.58	1.35	1.26

Conclusions:

1. Among the different types of drill paddy-based cropping system cultivation group higher percentage of illiteracy was observed in the farmers adopted drill paddy- latharus cropping system (26.66%) followed by drill paddy-linseed group (19.99%) and drill paddy-gram (6.66%).
2. Percentage of farmers having graduate level education was highest in the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system (13.33%) followed by drill paddy-linseed and drill paddy- latharus cropping systems (6.66%).
3. The average size of holding of the group of farmers adopted the drill paddy-gram cropping system was 2.52 hectare followed by drill paddy-linseed 2.08 hectare and drill paddy-latharus 1.82 hectare.
4. The highest cropping intensity was observed in the farmers group adopted drill paddy- gram cropping system (197.37%) followed by drill paddy - linseed (195.79%), and drill paddy-latharus cropping system (190.32%) respectively.
5. Paddy occupied 52.54 % area of GCA in the group of farmers adopted drill paddy-latharus cropping system followed by farmers group of drill paddy-linseed (51.07%), and drill paddy-gram (50.66%) respectively.
6. The average investments in fixed assets by the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system was Rs 10,73000/farm

followed by drill paddy-linseed cropping system Rs.9,01500/farm, and for drill paddy-latharus Rs. 7,96000/farm respectively.

7. The highest gross returns received to farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system i.e. Rs.1,40000/- per hectare followed by drill paddy-linseed Rs 97,570/-, and drill paddy-latharus cropping system Rs.87,600/-.
8. Highest per hectare net returns at cost A realised by the farmers adopted drill paddy-gram cropping system Rs.88,505.05/- followed by paddy- linseed Rs.57,100.89/- and paddy-latharus Rs.46,263.35/- .
9. The highest BC ratio was realised by the farmers adopted drill paddy- gram cropping system at Cost A, Cost B and Cost C respectively followed by drill paddy-linseed and drill paddy-latharus cropping system.

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